
PT.ON.DATA platform and Requirements for the New Proposed Solution

Report created under the project

SSD2 and FoodEx2 compliant real-time registration and classification of food sampling data - improving data quality for risk assessment (Pilot Project)

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Context

The present document was created as a specification for the National Data Management Systems (NDMS) referred as PT.ON.DATA. This platform was developed under previous EFSA projects with the purpose of creating a system capable of managing analytical data from food and feed, while proving means through its modules and tools to store and process these data following the EFSA's defined Standard Sample Description 2 (SSD2) specification for data transmission.

The PT.ON.DATA platform has gone through multiple phases of improvement, which happened throughout the years, and recently with the participation of Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge, I.P. (INSA) as one of the partners on the project "SSD2 and FoodEx2 compliant real-time registration and classification of food sampling data - improving data quality for risk assessment", it was defined as a goal for this project, and agreed by all partners, that the PT.ON.DATA platform should be used as the NDMS to be further developed and satisfy the goals, described below, of this new project:

- Improve/Restructure the dynamic sampling forms module;
- Develop the application that will run on the mobile devices;
- Prepare/Improve the existing system in order to receive the data submitted through the mobile app;
- Prepare/Improve the existing system so real-time communication with the mobile devices that are on the field is possible;
- Data filled using digital sampling forms, must be able to be exported to a physical format;
- Implement interfaces between systems (NDMSs) so a two-way communication is possible;
- Plan and implement an automatic PT.ON.DATA FoodEx2 classification system for sampling descriptions.

In order to have these goals met, a process of system analysis took place where the infrastructure in which the PT.ON.DATA was built upon, as well as software and tools used for its development, each aspect of the platform was considered and after the long process of deliberation by the development team, it was decided that a new system would be the best solution for the case at hand. The development of a new system that could easily communicate with existing NDMS, similar to PT.ON.DATA, would be the ideal approach, which in turn would remove the need to re-structure and re-define an older system. As a result, the development team began defining the requirements for this new system. This document will briefly describe how PT.ON.DATA helped with the definition and implementation of a new system.

Database

PT.ON.DATA is a web-based platform, meaning that its user interface can be accessed via a web browser, as such to its users it only delivers web pages as interfaces to communicate with internal data. PT.ON.DATA internal database include tables and other data structures with information only related to analytical food data that will eventually be transformed to follow the SSD2 standard. Interestingly, this analytical food data is basically data which contain information of food samples that were collected on the field. This sample data, before entering the PT.ON.DATA platform, was first inserted into another NDMS for validation and processing. However, since the goal of the IDRisk project is to create a system capable of dynamically and digitally assist in collection sample data directly from the field, the IDRisk system could, through the implementation of interfaces, feed data into the PT.ON.DATA platform. We this functionality in mind, PT.ON.DATA database and data workflow was taken into account when developing as new system that could feed others NDMS.

Figure 1 - PT.ON.DATA data workflow

For the IDRisk system, the new database would follow a similar structure in which a hierarchy of users had be taken into account in order to have different layers of access and functionalities. The ability to control the access and use of certain modules was very requested feature for PT.ON.DATA and should be kept as an important feature for the IDRisk system. Along with tables and data structures related to the systems users, tables to stored sampling form definition and their data had also to be created.

Figure 2 - IDRisk system database structure

Contained within this database are also supplementary table dedicated to store information related to the several types of operations that could be applied and would represent the status the created digital sample forms. From beginning of the sampling process, where data is collected and inserted into the IDRisk application, until it reaches the defined operator user that will validate that data, forms can go from different states and pass through different users, and as a result, all these paths and changes together with the information of what user was handling the information at each state, these types of information should be present in the database for traceability and management purposes.

The IDRisk system differs from PT.ON.DATA went it comes to what type of data it also stores. The IDRisk system will also stores sample data through the use of the Forms that are created within it, but to actually be able to create a Form and use it on another occasion within this system, the form structure, which includes the definition of every element contained in it, as well as other properties such as position, size, etc., this information has to be stored in its internal tables. This was the challenge posed by the IDRisk project, the challenge of how to store this dynamic structure that could be edit at any time. The development decided that a solution for this necessity was to save the form definition in a *json* into the form's table.

System Requirements

The first phase of the development consisted on a series of meetings to stablish what the system should do and how it should do it. An assessment of the system goal led to the definition of the system requirements and specifications. These requirements were organized into functional requirements and non-functional requirements, and were prioritized through three levels: High, Medium, and Low. The following tables (Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3) present the initial main requirements that the system’s development team defined together with the project partners. Important to note: due to the large scope of the project, the presented requirements changed overtime, with more requirements being added through the development process.

Table 1 - Funcional Requirements

ID	Functional Requirements	Priority
1	The system should allow the creation of new users.	High
2	The system should only allow access to its features through an authentication page.	High
3	The system should contain 3 types of roles for their users: Administrator, Manager and Inspector.	High
4	The system should allow any user with the role “Administrator” to create new users.	High
5	The system should allow any user with the role “Administrator” to delete existing users.	High
6	The system should allow any user with the role “Administrator” to edit the profile of existing users.	High
7	The system should have an application/module for Form Creation	High
8	The system should have an application/module for Form Management	High
9	The system should have an application/module for Operation Management	High
10	The system should have an application/module in which the inspectors would use the created Forms	High
11	The system should allow any user with the role “Administrator” to use any module/application with the IDRisk system	High
12	The system should allow any user with the role “Manager” to use the Operation Management	High

	module/application as well as the Inspector module/application for Form usage	
13	The system should allow any user with the role “Inspector” to only use the inspector’s module/application	High
14	The Form Creation module/application should allow dynamically placement of input field objects in order to replicate a paper Form	High
15	The Form Creation module/application should allow any previously created Form to be edited or deleted	High
16	The Form Creation module/application should contain dynamic input field capable of listing values from other sources (Files or Databases)	High
17	The Form Creation module/application should contain image input fields to upload pictures that were taken from mobile devices	High
18	The Form Creation module/application should contain GPS input fields to gather the location from which the sampling operation is taking place	High
19	The Inspector’s application/module should be able to run/execute on mobile devices	High
20	The Inspector’s application/module should be able to run/execute on mobile devices with and without internet access	High
21	The Inspector’s application/module should be able to send inserted data on the Forms to the server in Internet connection is available	High
22	The Inspector’s application/module should be able to store internally on the mobile devices data that is inserted via the Digital Form in case there is no Internet connection	High
23	The Inspector’s application/module should be able send stored information when no Internet was available to the server once internet connection is restored	High
24	The Inspector’s application/module should be able export the filled in Form to be printed when a printer is connected to the mobile device	High
25	The Inspector’s application/module should be able annex other files to the filled in Form	Medium
26	The Form Creation module/application should give the possibility of defining which fields are required	High
27	The Form Creation module/application should give the possibility of defining rules/events for	High

	when a certain field has a certain value, other set of defined fields should be automatically filled in with data from also defined sources (Files or Databases)	
28	The IDRisk system should have an API for others system to use and consume its data	High
29	The Form Creation module/application should possess a FoodEx2 input field to allow the user to insert FoodEx2 codes related to the sample	High
30	The IDRisk system should notify its users (depending on their roles) of changes and events occurring in the system via email	Low
31	The Form Creation module/application should possess a BarCode reader input field	Medium

Table 2 - Non-Functional Requirements

ID	Non-Functional Requirements	Priority
1	The system's interface should be fast, responsive and adapt to different resolutions	High
2	The system should have its interface in the following languages: Portuguese and Croatian	High
3	The system shouldn't allow any user not authenticated to use any of the applications/modules	High
4	The system should mobile devices to connect the applications/module through Wifi and other mobile connections (ex.: 2G,3G etc.)	High
5	The system should contain manuals and how to use documents	High
6	The system should mobile devices to use any type of printer (directly connected or through some network access)	High
7	The Inspector's application should be very simple and easy to use	Medium
8	The Inspector's application should not have poor performance in order to avoid consuming too much battery from the device	Medium